

Mechanism of Rearrangement of Heterocyclic *N*-Oxides

Binod Kumar Varma and A. B. Lal

The rearrangement of 2-methylpyridine-*N*-oxide¹ in acetic anhydride afforded a mixture of two esters (II and III), which, on hydrolysis and fractional distillation, furnished 2-hydroxymethylpyridino (I) and 2-methyl-6-hydroxypyridine (IV). The isolation of (IV) has been reported only by the Japanese group² and not by other workers^{1,3,4}.

Several mechanisms^{1,4,5} have been proposed for this rearrangement but these suffer from the defect that the formation of (IV) has been overlooked by all. Further, according to the current views⁴, the rearrangement proceeds through a radical process. On the other hand, Margraf⁶ suggested that pyridine *N*-oxide could rearrange through either of the pathways involving free ions or ion pairs. It will be thus apparent that (II) is produced by the former and (III) by the latter, i.e., by two entirely different and competing pathways. Moreover, we found that 2-methylpyridine-*N*-oxide does not react with benzoyl chloride in a Schotten-Baumann reaction although 2-methylquinoline-*N*-oxide does react to provide 2-benzoyloxymethylquinoline.¹⁰ Therefore, the analogy of the anhydro-base theory^{1,4,5,7-11} does not appear reasonable. The *N*-acetoxy-2-methylpyridinium cation as perchlorate salt has been isolated recently by Traynelis and Pacini¹², who have also attempted kinetic study of the rearrangement. A satisfactory mechanism does not seem to have evolved from their study.

It is suggested that acetic anhydride first removes a proton¹³ from 2-methylpyridine *N*-oxide and the resulting electron localisation on the nitrogen enable the oxygen to add on a proton.

- (I) R=OH; R'=H.
 (II) R=OOC.CH₃; R'=H.
 (III) R=H; R'=OOC.Me.
 (IV) R=H; R'=OH.

1. Bockelheide and Linn., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **76**, 1286.
2. Kobayashi and Furukawa, *Chem. Abs.*, 1955, **49**, 10948c.
3. Bullitt and Maynard, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **76**, 1370.
4. Oae *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1962, **84**, 3359.
5. Traynelis and Martello, *ibid.*, 1958, **80**, 6590.
6. Margraf *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1963, **85**, 958.
7. Oae *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1962, **84**, 3362.
8. Berson and Cohen., *ibid.*, 1955, **77**, 1281.
9. Traynelis and Martello, *ibid.*, 1960, **82**, 2744.
10. Hence, *Ber.*, 1936, **69**, 534.
11. Fichter, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 3026.
12. V. J. Traynelis and Pacini, *Ibid.*, 1964, **86**, 4917.
13. Lal and Petrow, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949 (Supplementary issue No. 1) 115.

Then an anionotropic rearrangement follows affording the hydroxymethyl derivative (I). Finally, acetylium ion reacts with (I) to provide the ester (II). A similar path can be

envisaged in the case of the *N*-acetoxy cation which would rearrange directly as the anion CH_3COO^- migrates. This mechanism falls in line with other anionotropic rearrangements. Formation of (III) occurs when the anion (OH^-) goes to the 6-position which acquires a small positive charge due to localisation of electron pair on the nitrogen. This is followed by elimination of a proton and attack by the acetylium ion. It will be evident that this competing reaction cannot provide a good yield of (III) and such is the case.

The rearrangement of 2-methylquinoline *N*-oxide under the mild conditions of the Schotten-Baumann reaction follows a similar path, leading to the formation of the ester corresponding to (II).¹⁰ But this does not occur in the case of 2-methylpyridine *N*-oxide as methyl group is less reactive and drastic conditions are necessary.

One more substance (m.p. 199-201°C) has now been isolated from the rearranged products obtained from 4-methylpyridine *N*-oxide. Further work, therefore, appears necessary before the mechanism of this rearrangement is settled.

2-Methyl-6-hydroxypyridine (IV).—The rearranged products (53 g.) taken in HCl (conc., 530 ml.), was refluxed for 8 hrs. It was slowly evaporated and the residue, dissolved in chloroform (200 ml.), was treated with an aqueous paste of K_2CO_3 . The chloroform solution was dried (Na_2SO_4) and the solvent removed. The residual liquid was fractionally distilled to furnish (I) (23 g., 60%), b.p. 98-102°/7mm.

Another fraction was collected (b.p. 150-55°/9 mm.) as a highly viscous pale yellow oil, which gradually solidified into yellow crystals (6.5 g., 17%). Crystallisation from benzene-acetone produced shining white crystals, m.p. 166-68° (lit.^{11,14-17}, m.p. 163-65°, 158-59°, 158°, 158.5°, 159°) (Found: C, 65.6; H, 5.95. $\text{C}_6\text{H}_7\text{NO}$ requires C, 66.06; H, 6.42%). The IR spectrum of this compound was recorded on KBr disc on a Perkin Elmer grating IR spectrometer, Model 237. A broad peak at 3425 cm^{-1} indicated monomeric NH and there was a similar broad band in the carbonyl region at 1755 cm^{-1} . The broad band¹⁸ extending from $3100\text{-}2400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ was characteristic of an α -pyridone.

The authors thank the Patna University for grants and research scholarship to one of them (B.K.V.) and to Dr. J. N. Chatterjee for IR spectra.

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
PATNA UNIVERSITY,
PATNA-5.

Received April 21, 1966.

14. Adams and Schrecker, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 71, 1186.

15. Franke and Kraft, *Ber.*, 1953, 86, 797.

16. Moore and Marlon, *Chem. Abs.*, (see No. 2) 1954, 48, 12129a.

17. Errera, *Ber.*, 1900, 33, 2969.

18. "Infrared Absorption Spectroscopy", Koji Nakanishi, Holden-day, Inc., San Francisco and Nankodo Comp. Ltd., Tokyo, 1962, p. 207.